

Enhancing large-area photoelectrochemical cells' performance through conductivity improvement of customizable FTO collectors grid

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Upscaling PEC devices faces challenges in maintaining performance and stability.
- Highly conductive customizable FTO collectors offer a compatible solution.
- Large area DSSCs demonstrated improved efficiency and 1000 h stability.
- Large area PEC-WS systems achieved higher photocurrent and stable operation over 100 h.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Photoelectrochemical cells, including dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) and water-splitting systems (PEC-WS), offer the significant advantage of directly converting solar energy into electricity and/or fuel. However, their commercial viability is limited by upscaling challenges, particularly due to the reliance on transparent conductive electrodes, which allow for effective visible light transmission and charge collection yet display ohmic losses arising from the electrical resistance across larger dimensions substrates. Identifying an alternative electrode material suitable across PEC technologies has been challenging due to manufacturing requirements and long-term photostability incompatibility.

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In this study, we developed and evaluated fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO)-coated glass substrates integrated with FTO current collectors as an efficient and stable strategy for upscaling PEC devices. Multiphysics simulations were employed to assess various FTO mesh designs, evaluating the impact of collector density and geometry on the conductivity of the FTO substrates. The optimized configurations were implemented on FTO-coated glasses via ultrasonic spray-pyrolysis, with deposition parameters finely tuned. Large-area DSSCs and PEC-WS devices, featuring a photoactive area of 25 cm², were assembled with FTO-mesh substrates and exhibited a stable operation with best-performing designs, achieving solar energy conversion efficiencies *ca.* 2.1 and 1.2 times, respectively higher than collector-less DSSC and PEC-WS reference counterparts.

1. Introduction

A photoelectrochemical cell (PEC) harnesses light energy to drive chemical reactions that generate electricity or produce valuable chemicals. Typically, a PEC consists of a junction between a semiconductor and an electrolyte, usually a liquid containing a suitable redox pair with one or more oxidation states. In such a device, at least one electrode is composed of a photoactive semiconductor material capable of absorbing light and generating electron-hole pairs [1,2]. PCEs can be broadly classified into photoelectrochemical photovoltaics (PEC-PV) and photoelectrolytic cells [2,3], as illustrated in Fig. S1. In a PEC-PV, the charge separation is utilized to generate electrical energy. An example of this is a dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC), which comprises a mesoporous semiconductor film (usually titanium dioxide – TiO₂) sensitized with dye as the working electrode (WE) that, upon photon absorption, ejects an electron into the semiconductor conduction band, simultaneously oxidizing the iodide/triiodide (I⁻/I₃⁻) electrolyte. After the energy depletion, the electron is reintroduced to the cell circuit via the catalytic counter electrode (CE, typically platinum – Pt), regenerating the electrolytes' charge – Fig. S1a [4,5]. On the other hand, in a photoelectrolytic cell, the charge separation is used to produce added-value fuels, available for later electrochemical discharge or use as a chemical feedstock [2,3,6]. An example is a photoelectrochemical water splitting (PEC-WS) device. In these cells, the WE consists of a medium-to-wide bandgap semiconductor (such as hematite α -Fe₂O₃) responsible for light-absorption, charge separation and water oxidation (to oxygen – O₂); a dark CE made of a metal-based catalytic material suitable for hydrogen (H₂) evolution (typically Pt); and an internal separator (usually an ion-exchange membrane or a diaphragm) to ensure internal ion balance and physically separate the H₂ and O₂ products – Fig. 1b [7–9]. The integrated nature of the PEC-WS cell technology, combining solar energy harvesting and conversion in a single package, has the potential to offer a cost-efficient approach for (green) H₂ production, especially when coupled with solar concentration and thermal management strategies [10]. Furthermore, DSSCs are promising for both outdoor and indoor electricity generation due to robust photovoltaic performance under diffuse and artificial light [11,12]. Moreover, integrating DSSCs into a photoelectrolytic cell can yield a dual-absorber, tandem PEC-WS configuration [13]. With careful material selection, complementary light-absorption capabilities and energy-level alignment, such configurations can more effectively overcome the high potential required to drive unbiased water splitting (>1.5 V) [14]. These technologies showcase some of the potential of harnessing light energy for a wide range of applications, including power generation, sunlight-to-electro fuels, and the production of clean fuels [4,8,13].

A critical component in DSSCs and PEC-WS technologies is the use of transparent conductive oxides (TCO) as the substrate material. Among available TCOs, fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) has a unique combination of supreme thermal and chemical stability, electrical conductivity, and transparency. Commercial FTO-coated glass substrates have sheet resistance in the 7–15 Ω sq⁻¹ range with visible-spectrum transmissions of 85–89 % for 0.5–0.7 μ m FTO layer thicknesses [15]. These electrical and optical properties are essential for PEC devices: high conductivity facilitates efficient charge collection and minimizes losses during electron transport, while high transparency ensures that most of the incident

light reaches the photoactive semiconductor layers, maximizing light absorption. However, when the area of FTO substrates increases, the extended current pathways result in higher overall electrical resistance.

This FTO scaling issue underscores the limitation of PEC systems of struggling to maintain photovoltaic performance in varying-sized devices. In the case of DSSCs, small-scale devices (<1 cm²) are typically used to achieve high power conversion efficiencies (η_{PCE}) in academic research, with a certified maximum η_{PCE} of 13 % [16]. However, the η_{PCE} drastically drops to less than 1 % for a 42 cm² single cell using a bare FTO substrate [17]. A similar trend is observed for PEC-WS devices, particularly those based on metal-oxide semiconductors [18]. For instance, the current record for photocurrent-density in a small-scale (<0.5 cm²) nanostructured α -Fe₂O₃ photoanodes is *ca.* 6 mA cm⁻² (at 1.23 V_{RHE}, AM 1.5G light – 100 mW cm⁻²) [19], however, there are no reports aiming at their upscaling, mainly due to low reproducibility of

Fig. 1. SEM images of the FTO films deposited on ordinary glass at (a) 400 °C, (b) 420 °C, (c) 440 °C, (d) 460 °C, (e) 480 °C and (f) 500 °C using precursor solution with Fluorine content of 20 %.

the deposition procedure. In fact, for $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films prepared by spray pyrolysis, the largest area reported is 100 cm^2 , corresponding to a current reduction exceeding 65 % compared to smaller devices.

The upscaling behavior of PEC-WS and DSSCs can be modeled using the one-diode equation, also known as the Shockley diode equation, which mathematically describes the current density-potential (J - V) characteristics of a semiconductor junction diode [20,21]. The model consists of a photocurrent source J_{photo} , a diode described by the single-exponential Shockley equation [22], shunt resistance (R_{shunt}), and series resistance (R_{series}) – Fig. S2. The J - V characteristic of the solar device is given by an implicit nonlinear equation as follows [23]:

$$J = J_{\text{photo}} - J_0 \cdot \left(e^{\frac{F \cdot (V + J \cdot R_{\text{series}})}{n \cdot k \cdot T}} - 1 \right) - \left(\frac{V + J \cdot R_{\text{series}}}{R_{\text{shunt}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where J_0 is the reverse saturated current, F is the Faraday constant, n is the diode ideality factor, R is the universal gas constant, $k = 1.381 \times 10^{-23}\text{ J K}^{-1}$, and T is the absolute temperature. For an ideal solar device, R_{shunt} would be infinite, eliminating any alternative path for current flow, while the R_{series} would be zero, ensuring no additional voltage drop before the load [24]. In practice, impurities and defects upon device assembly can adversely affect the R_{shunt} . Although, the R_{series} can arise from various sources – including as the electron transport associated with the counter electrode and electrolyte – the dominant culprit often lies with its very foundation: the current extraction from the electrode [25]. Even in highly optimized conditions, the FTO's inherent resistivity directly translates to a voltage drop when current flows through the substrate, which can be computed using eq. (2) [26]:

$$V = V_0 - J \cdot R_{\text{series}} = V_0 - J \cdot \frac{R_{\text{sheet}} \cdot W}{L} \quad (2)$$

where V_0 is the cells' potential considering null resistance, and R_{sheet} , W , and L are, respectively, the sheet resistance, width, and length of the glass substrate. As the substrate size increases, the overall R_{series} also rises, leading to a more pronounced potential drop across the device, thereby affecting the PEC's overall efficiency. A graphical representation of the impact of the substrate size and R_{sheet} on eq. (1) and eq. (2) is illustrated in Fig. S3.

The drawback of upscaling can be mitigated through advances in material and design strategies. One approach to enhance the conductivity is increasing the FTO thickness [27] or inserting a more conductive intermediate layer [28]. However, this modification can reduce light transmittance and decrease photogeneration [29]. Another option is to use alternative TCOs such as indium-doped tin oxide (ITO) or aluminum-doped zinc oxide (AZO) [30]; however, their implementation requires careful consideration due to potential compatibility issues during the fabrication of the semiconductor. Despite its high conductivity and transparency, ITO is limited by the scarcity and high cost of indium, posing significant challenges for large-scale production [31,32]. In contrast, AZO is cost-effective and abundant but exhibits lower electrical conductivity and transparency [33,34]. Moreover, AZO films are prone to stability issues under harsh environmental conditions, such as the elevated temperatures required for sintering TiO_2 and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ layers (up to $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively) [35–37]. At these temperature, both ITO and AZO lose conductivity [38,39], whereas the electrical and optical properties of FTO are preserved [40]. Various techniques can be employed to deposit FTO onto glass substrate, including chemical vapor deposition [41], magnetron sputtering [42], sol-gel [43], and spray pyrolysis [44]. Notably, the scalability of the ultrasonic spray pyrolysis (USP) method has been demonstrated in previous studies [45,46]. This process allows for precise control over film thickness, uniformity, and morphology by adjusting parameters such as precursor concentration, substrate temperature, and spray flow rate. By optimizing these parameters, FTO films with low resistivity and high transmittance can be produced as a strategy to obtain high-performing devices [44,47,48]. For optimized FTO coatings, the

R_{sheet} typically falls within $2\text{--}4\ \Omega\ \text{sq}^{-1}$ [47,49]. However, even with this conductivity improvement, devices still, theoretically, exhibit under-performance, as illustrated in Fig. S3b. A design-wise strategy involves incorporating grid patterns of low-resistance busbars or current collectors. This approach shortens the path for charge flow, reducing the electrical resistance [50,51], and, through optimized grid design, ensures a uniform current distribution across the electrode [26,46,47]. Embedding electrodes with a highly conductive mesh has been a standard practice since the first generation of solar cell technology [51–53]. In fact, record-breaking silicon solar cells typically integrate metal grids (silver, copper) [54,55]. The choice of material for busbars and collectors depends on factors such as conductivity, cost, compatibility with the device components, and the requirements of the production steps.

Metallic elements are commonly used in solid heterojunction devices, and their incorporation into the WE of PEC devices has been shown to offer benefits, such as more efficient separation of electron-hole pairs and plasmonic effects [56,57]. However, when employed as a collector, metals encounter significant obstacles, namely chemical interaction with PEC components, corrosion, and increased recombination [58–61]. To mitigate these issues, metallic collectors require protective layers – a solution that must be carefully addressed to be compatible with PEC manufacturing processes and meet long-term stability requirements [62,63]. Only a few studies have reported on sophisticated titanium/chromium and nickel collectors in DSSCs [64,65], while PEC-WS systems have explored the application of metal foils, such as iron, copper, tungsten and tantalum [66–68], and grid collectors made of silver, nickel and copper [21,68,69]. Unfortunately, the long-term stability due to metal corrosion, recombination, and problems with adhesion to FTO/glass substrates causes concerns about the prospects of metal current collectors in PECs [6,70].

An overlooked solution may lie in using FTO as the collector material. FTO is already widely employed as the transparent conductive electrode and has demonstrated excellent electrochemical stability under continuous illumination in DSSCs and PEC-WS systems [71–74]. Furthermore, FTO can be fabricated using scalable, cost-effective techniques such as spray pyrolysis [75]. However, producing a mesh collector via a lift-off process introduces a critical challenge: it requires a masking material capable of withstanding the optimal deposition temperature of approximately $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ needed to achieve a conductive FTO layer [76]. In this work, we demonstrate a method for fabricating current collectors made entirely of FTO on FTO-coated glass substrates, ensuring compatibility with various PEC technologies, including DSSCs and PEC-WS. Multiphysics simulations were employed to optimize the grid design by exploring different geometries and sizes, thereby addressing FTO's lower conductivity compared to metals. The resulting FTO current collectors exhibit remarkable versatility, paving the way for effective upscaling of PEC applications.

2. Experimental

2.1. FTO deposition

FTO deposition was performed by ultrasonic spray pyrolysis (USP). Spray solution was prepared by dissolving $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals (98 % purity, Thermo Scientific) in absolute ethanol (LiChrosolv; Sigma-Aldrich) to obtain a concentration of 0.2 M. Powder of NH_4F (96 %; Alfa Aesar) was added to tin chloride ethanol solution as the dopant and stirred continuously for 5 h. A $5 \times 5\text{ cm}^2$ soda-lime glass (2.2 mm thick) was cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with 10 % ethanol solution of KOH for 15 min and rinsed with distilled water. The ultrasonic spray pyrolysis system (ExactaCoat OP3; Sono-Tek) consisted of a 25 kHz nozzle mounted on an X-Y position software-controlled arm, plugged into an air compressor to control the shape and spray mist, and a syringe pump to deliver the precursor solution at a constant feed rate. The nozzle was 100 mm from the substrates, positioned on a hotplate heated to the desired temperature, and stabilized for 30 min. 50 mL of precursor

solution was sprayed with liquid injection and compressed air flow rates of 1 and 3 mL min⁻¹, respectively. The spray path consisted of two parallel, straight 5 cm segments, 2.5 cm apart, with nozzle power and head's speed set to 3 W and 10 mm s⁻¹, respectively. The variables for FTO deposition optimization were the substrate temperature and the fluoride dopant molar ratio relative to SnCl₄.

2.2. Deposition of FTO current collectors

Fig. S4 illustrates the deposition steps of the current collectors of FTO. FTO-coated substrates (TEC7; Greatcell Solar) were cut and cleaned (a). The samples were then coated with an anthracite heat-resistant ink (b) and dried at 150 °C for 2 h (c). The collector design pattern was formed by selectively removing the mask (d) with laser ablation (LaserMaq), and the sample was ultrasonically cleaned with diluted KOH (e). The substrate was then ultrasonically sprayed with a 0.2 M SnCl₄ solution containing 20 % fluoride dopant at 450 °C (f). After cooling to room temperature, the mask was removed by immersing the deposited samples for 8 h in a 10 % KOH solution in ethanol at 50 °C (g). The samples were then thoroughly cleaned with distilled water (h).

2.3. Numerical simulations

The electrical conductivity of the FTO collectors (Fig. S5) was assessed by simulating the potential across the substrate using the AC/DC module of COMSOL Multiphysics® software (version 6.2 license number 17079237). The physics module uses the finite element method to solve the current conservation equation based on Ohm's law, with the scalar electric potential (a single value representing the electric potential at each point in the system) as the dependent variable [77].

The conservation of current is described by the equation of continuity [78]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the current density vector and ρ is the space charge density. When the current is steady, there is no time variation and $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = 0$, this results in:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0 \quad (4)$$

in a stationary state, the current density is directly related to the strength of the field applied (analogous to Ohm's law) [79]:

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma \cdot \mathbf{E} \quad (5)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity, and \mathbf{E} is the electric field vector.

Considering a point, \mathbf{r} , in the electric field, the electric potential is given by the line integral:

$$V = - \int_{\mathcal{C}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathcal{C} \quad (6)$$

where is an arbitrary path (along $d\mathcal{C}$) from some fixed reference point to \mathbf{r} .

According to the Maxwell-Faraday equation in electrostatics, the rotational component of the electric field ($\nabla \times \mathbf{E}$) is zero, indicating that the electric field is conservative [78]. As a result, the line integral above is determined by its endpoints rather than a specific path, making the V well-defined everywhere. Thus, the gradient theorem allows us to write:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla V \quad (7)$$

Replacing eq. (5) and eq. (7) into the continuity equation gives:

$$-\nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla V) = 0 \quad (8)$$

These equations collectively describe how the electric potential varies within a material, ensuring that the current is conserved

according to Ohm's law.

2.4. Preparation of dye-sensitized solar cells

Working electrodes (WE) for DSSCs were prepared by screen-printing with RP 2.2 RokuPrint, GmbH, a size of 25 cm² of Greatcell Solar titania pastes, a transparent mesoporous layer (18NR-T), and an opaque atop (18NR-AO) layer onto commercial TEC7 substrates and lab-made FTO-collector substrates and sintered at 500 °C for 1 h. Sensitization was performed by immersing the WE substrates in a solution of 0.5 mM N719 dye and 5 mM chenodeoxycholic acid (Solaronix) in absolute ethanol for 24 h. The counter electrodes (CE) were prepared by magnetron sputtering a thin (0.1 μm) platinum layer onto TEC7. Afterward, the WE were sealed with the CE with a thermoplastic film (Meltonix 1161-60, DuPont Byne) in a hot press. Iodide/tri-iodide electrolyte, based on a 3-methoxypropionitrile solvent (Iodolyte Z-150, Solaronix), was injected into the cells through the holes in CE; injection holes were closed with thermoplastic film and lamella glass.

2.5. Preparation of hematite photoanodes

Prior to hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) deposition, a conductive silver paste frame (Ferro GmbH GSSP SP 1963) was manually printed on both sides of the edges of the FTO-coated glass substrates under study (with or without the FTO current collectors; Greatcell Solar®, 2.2 mm thick, TEC-7) and later air-annealed for 30 min at 500 °C. Afterward, these substrates were placed on a heating plate and heated to 500 °C (corresponding to a measured surface temperature of 400 °C on the substrate), and a TEOS solution (tetraethyl orthosilicate, Sigma-Aldrich, volume fraction of 10 % in ethanol, 20 mL) was hand-sprayed, followed by a 30 min annealing step. For the ultrathin bare α -Fe₂O₃ film deposition by ultrasonic spray pyrolysis (USP), the following procedure was used: i) The TEOS-treated samples were placed below the USP spray nozzle (50 mm from the substrates, powered to 5 W, shaping gas at 2 mL min⁻¹), maintaining the same heating plate temperature; ii) during the deposition procedure, the spray head moved over the samples at a speed of 20 mm s⁻¹, while a syringe pump was used to feed the moving nozzle with a 10 mM solution of Fe(acac)₃ (iron (III) acetylacetonate, 99.9 %, Sigma-Aldrich) in EtOH at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹; and iii) a total of ca. 40 mL of precursor solution was deposited during this procedure, resulting in a cooled α -Fe₂O₃ thin-film thickness of ca. 30 nm (estimated by UV-visible absorption data) [80].

2.6. Characterization

The R_{sheet} was determined using the Van Der Pauw method by applying current and measuring the voltage along the FTO film with SourceMeter 2400, Keithley. The film thickness (t) was estimated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with SEM-EDS FEI QUANTA 400 FEG ESEM/EDAX Genesis X4M (Fig. S6). The resistivity of lab-made FTO was obtained using eq. (9):

$$\rho = R_{\text{sheet}} \times t \quad (9)$$

The J - V curves of DSSCs were recorded at 25 ± 1 °C using Zahner ZENNIUM electrochemical station with a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Simulated solar illumination was provided by Newport 92193-1000 solar simulator equipped with an AM1.5G filter and. The irradiance was calibrated using Si photodiode and adjusted to 97 mW cm⁻² over a square shape area of 8 × 8 cm². This represented the maximum irradiance output achievable due to the lamp aging effects. Photogenerated conversion efficiency and FF were calculated using the following equations:

$$\eta_{\text{PCE}} = \frac{V_{\text{oc}} \times J_{\text{sc}}}{I_s} \times \eta_{\text{FF}} \quad (10)$$

$$\eta_{FF} = \frac{P_{MPP}}{V_{OC} \times J_{SC}} \quad (11)$$

where the V_{OC} is the open circuit potential, the J_{SC} is the short circuit current, FF is the Fill Factor (eq. (11)), and the P_{MPP} represents the maximum power point (MPP), which is the highest value attained by the product of $J \times V$.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed in DSSC with Autolab/PGSTAT302N workstation (Metrohm, Switzerland) in dark conditions from 100 kHz to 0.05 Hz by applying a peak-to-peak sinusoidal perturbation of 10 mV at open circuit potential (V_{OC}). Impedance parameters were computed using ZView® software and fitting the EIS response to an equivalent circuit model, depicted in Fig. S7, which includes four processes [81]: i) charge transfer at the counter electrode (R_{CE}) recognized at high frequencies, ii) electron transport in the TiO_2 layer and the electron-hole recombination ($R_{WE,k}$) measured at medium frequencies, iii) diffusion into the electrolyte process observable at very low frequencies given by the Warburg element (W_s), and iv) another resistance (R_{Series}) attributed to the electrical conductivity of the system.

The water-splitting performance of the prepared $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanodes was evaluated by J - V and EIS measurements performed under a three-electrode setup (Fig. S8). To perform such tests, the developed $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanodes, an Ag/AgCl/Sat KCl reference electrode (Metrohm, Switzerland), and a platinized-Ti mesh counter electrode were immersed in a 1 M KOH aqueous solution (VWR, 25 °C, pH = 13.5) inside a “Portocell” PEC-WS device [82]. The J - V characteristic curves were then obtained by applying an external potential bias to the cell (scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹) and measuring the generated photocurrent using an Autolab/PGSTAT302N workstation. The measurements were performed at room temperature both in the dark and under 1 sun simulated sunlight (100 mW cm⁻², Sulphur plasma lamp, system AS 1300 V 2.0, Plasma International GmbH). EIS analysis was carried out in the dark and at the V_{OC} , using the same electrochemical station to apply a sinusoidal potential perturbation with an amplitude of 10 mV and record the system’s response over a frequency range of 0.1 Hz–100 kHz. Current extraction at the photoanode was possible through carefully positioned copper wires hand-welded to the Ag frame of the substrate. A waterproof epoxy resin (Araldite) protected the wires and the frame from the corrosive electrolyte.

The J - V curve data was used to estimate the power characteristics of the prepared photoanodes, as described elsewhere [83]. The light-induced photocurrent J_{photo} and photopotential V_{photo} were calculated from the measured light/dark current ($J_{light/dark}$) and potential ($V_{light/dark}$) using eqs. (12) and (13):

$$J_{photo} = J_{light} - J_{dark} \quad (12)$$

$$V_{photo}(J_{photo}) = V_{dark}(J_{photo}) - V_{light}(J_{photo}) \quad (13)$$

A plot of J_{photo} vs V_{photo} allows for the estimation of the short-circuit photocurrent (J_{sc}) and the open-circuit photopotential (V_{OC}). The product of $J_{photo} \times V_{photo}$ yields the light-induced electric power produced by the photoanode (P). A plot of P vs V_{photo} allows the identification of the maximum power point photopotential (V_{MPP}) and photocurrent (J_{MPP}) – Fig. S9. These parameters can be used to estimate the fill-factor of the J_{photo} vs V_{photo} curve, as shown in eq. (11).

The PEC efficiency of the device (η_{device}) was also estimated from J - V curve data. As proposed elsewhere [84,85], this metric is calculated from ratio between the energy of the produced hydrogen and the total energy input required to drive the water splitting reaction (solar energy and external bias) – eq. (14):

$$\eta_{device} = \left[\frac{J_{photo} \times 1.23}{I_s + (J_{photo} \times E_{bias})} \right] \quad (14)$$

where E_{bias} is the potential applied to the PEC system to obtain the J_{photo} ,

and I_s is the sunlight intensity (100 mW cm⁻²). Herein, E_{bias} is ca. 0.65 V_{NHE} , corresponding to an applied bias potential of ca. 1.45 V_{RHE} , in a KOH electrolyte solution (pH of ca. 13.5), usually associated to a photocurrent-density plateau for hematite photoelectrodes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fluorine-doped tin oxide current collectors

The SEM imaging of deposited FTO films, represented in Fig. 1a–f, revealed that the deposition temperature is the most impactful factor in the morphology of the FTO film. At temperatures up to 440 °C, the film is composed of particles with an apparent nanometric size. A qualitative transition in the morphology of the FTO happens above 460 °C with the formation of well-faceted crystals with μm -scaled sizes. The fluorine content in the precursor solution did not significantly impact on the FTO layer morphology (Fig. S10).

Fig. 2 shows the resistance of FTO obtained at different temperatures and fluorine content in the precursor solution. As expected, the resistivity drops with deposition temperature, declining from $74.3 \times 10^{-4} \Omega \text{ cm}$ to approximately $3.2 \times 10^{-4} \Omega \text{ cm}$ for samples obtained at 400 °C and 440 °C, respectively. The values agree with reports for FTO films deposited by the USP method [86–88]. Above 440 °C deposition temperature, the resistivity reaches a plateau. This outcome aligns with the

Fig. 2. FTO film resistivity as a function of (a) deposition temperature at a constant fluorine doping of 20 % and (b) fluorine content in precursor solution at a constant deposition temperature of 450 °C (Table S2 and S3).

observed SEM trends of enlarged grain size and reduced grain boundaries. The overall resistivity of FTO decreases with fluorine doping, a phenomenon consistent with the introduction of latroll-to-roll tice strains and defects [89]. This effect is particularly pronounced at doping levels below 10 % and turns to saturation at fluorine content above 20 %. Therefore, considering resistivity vs. Deposition temperature and fluorine content, a process temperature of 450 °C and 20 % of fluorine in precursor solution were selected for deposition of FTO current collectors. According to XRD study (Fig. S11), a well-crystallized cassiterite (tetragonal rutile-like structure) SnO_2 is formed at these deposition conditions.

Fig. 3a shows TEC7 substrate with an FTO line collectors arrangement produced using the mask design with a honeycomb structure. Fig. 3b provides a closer look at a single FTO line, revealing a width of ca. 800 μm . The FTO line width determines the PEC device's effective charge collection and transport area. FTO lines on TEC7 are polycrystalline with grains mostly aligned orthogonally to the substrate (Fig. 3c) and similar to the uniform film obtained on ordinary glass at 460 °C (Fig. 2). Fig. 3d provides a cross-sectional view of the collector line; the estimated thickness is ca. 5 μm . Current collector line thickness impacts the substrate's electrical conductivity, which is crucial for maintaining conductivity while preserving overall transparency.

3.2. Dye-sensitized solar cells with FTO-line collectors

Five FTO-coated glass substrates, each with dimensions of $6 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$ ($5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ of active area), were prepared with varying the number (n) of FTO line collectors – Fig. 4: i) Ref. – a reference sample, $n = 0$, with a commercial TEC7 ($7 \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) substrate; ii) Per. – a sample with a 5 mm wide FTO perimeter coating; iii) L2mm – a sample with $n = 2$, two FTO line collectors 2 mm wide; iv) L1mm – a sample with $n = 5$, five FTO line collectors 1 mm wide; v) L0.5 mm – a sample with $n = 11$, eleven FTO line collectors 0.5 mm wide. The number and width of FTO line collectors were designed to maintain a constant photoactive area of 90 % across all samples, ensuring that any observed differences in conductivity were due to the collector design rather than variations in active material coverage. The simulation was performed under steady-state conditions, assuming a uniform and isotropic conductivity for the FTO, estimated by linear interpolating resistivity values measured for USP-deposited FTO at 440 °C and 460 °C (Section 3.1), and a thickness of 5 μm . The boundaries at the upper and lower edges of the substrate

Fig. 3. (a) Photograph of FTO current collectors on TEC7 substrate. SEM imaging of FTO collector: (b) width, (c) morphology, (d) thickness.

Fig. 4. Photographs and contour maps of potential gradient simulations for different samples: (a) Ref., (b) Per., (c) L2mm, (d) L1mm, and (e) L0.5 mm.

were set as ground points, ensuring a fixed potential reference. A total current of 1 A was applied through a matrix of points within the photoactive area (Fig. S5). Temperature variations, surface roughness effects, and contact resistances were not considered to simplify the computational model. The results are represented in a contour color range, with red and blue representing the highest and lowest potential, providing the potential distribution across the FTO substrate. The computations of configurations with $n = 1$ to $n = 14$ are presented in Fig. S12.

Ideally, for efficient charge collection and minimal energy loss, the potential gradient should be as low and uniform as possible across the entire active area of the sample. The Reference exhibits a high potential

gradient difference along the substrate (Fig. 4a). Notably, the potential drop drastically withing ca. 1 cm distance, clearly pointing to the challenge of maintaining device performance using larger than that FTO substrates. Potential drop is reduced by adding an FTO perimeter

(Fig. 4b). The potential gradient appears to be more uniform in configurations with more collector lines that are narrower and closer together (Fig. 4c-e). This suggests that having more lines can help distribute the potential more evenly across the cell and facilitate a direct pathway for

Fig. 5. (a) J - V response, (b) Nyquist plot, and (c) normalized η_{PCE} history of DSSCs.

an efficient charge collection, substantially improving the conductivity from L2mm to L0.5 mm.

Selected designs of FTO current collectors were incarnated and used as photoanode substrates in DSSCs (Fig. S13)—Fig. 5a and 5b present the devices' J - V and EIS responses, respectively. The J - V curves for all configurations show similar V_{OC} (0.69–0.70 V), indicating that the energy difference between the Fermi level of the TiO_2 and the redox potential of the electrolyte is consistent across all configurations [90]. The photovoltaic performance of the cells (Table 1) is improved with increasing collector number n , as predicted by simulation. Overall η_{PCE} improvement is due to two well-distinguished contributions: i) an increase of the J_{SC} from 9.0 $mA\ cm^{-2}$ to 12.3–13.6 $mA\ cm^{-2}$, observed using the FTO perimeter (Per.) and the FTO-line configurations, with the L0.5 mm device showing the highest current density; and ii) an improved FF with the addition of FTO-lines. This indicates that lines are more effective at collecting and transporting charge carriers, even while removing active areas, leading to a higher power output. The net effect of these contributions is an increase of the η_{PCE} from 1.7 % (Ref.) to 3.5 % (L0.5 mm).

Nyquist plots of large-area DSSCs (Fig. 5b) show a classical pattern with three overlapped semicircles. Semicircles correspond to constant phase elements and respective resistances (Fig. S7) for charge transfer on CE, WE, and diffusion impedance; time constants appear one by one along high to low frequencies [91]. Mechanistic fitting of the spectra to an equivalent circuit is quite possible, but obtained values of low-frequency time constants will have little sense [64]. The applied current is poorly and non-uniformly distributed along the substrates (Fig. 4), making impedance response from the electrochemical processes uncertain for large-area substrates. The only element in the equivalent circuit not influenced by the electrochemical reactions is the R_{series} , determined by the intersection of the Nyquist curve with Z' axis at high frequencies (Table S4). R_{series} drops ca. 2 times, from 155 $\Omega\ cm^2$ in Ref. sample to 70 $\Omega\ cm^2$ for samples with FTO perimeter. FTO lines reduce R_{series} to 62 $\Omega\ cm^2$ for L0.5 mm sample. The enhanced charge extraction reduces the charge transfer resistance at the WE by facilitating electrons mobility, thereby minimizing recombination reaction with the electrolyte, as evidenced by the $R_{WE,k}$ seen in Table S4.

The current density increase, series resistance reduction, and FF improvement with increasing collector number n support the simulations' prediction (Fig. 4). Fig. 5c shows the ratio of η_{PCE} of DSSCs compared to its initial value (1 h after assembly) and over 1000 h of natural aging, stored under dark conditions. The devices with current collectors withstand 1000 h of aging and display full compatibility with DSSC components and aggressive iodide electrolytes. The increased normalized η_{PCE} within the first 350 h of aging is attributed to the stabilization of the photoanode/electrolyte interface, while electrolyte leakage/evaporation caused the PCE drop for the remainder of the period [71].

3.3. Photoelectrochemical water splitting with FTO-mesh collectors

The applicability of FTO lines as current collectors for up-scaled PEC-WS photoanodes was evaluated by employing the proposed multiphysics simulator to study the effect of geometry/pattern of FTO-mesh current collectors on the conductivity of $7 \times 7\ cm^2$ FTO-coated glass substrates ($5 \times 5\ cm^2$ of active area). Contrary to the case study presented for

DSSCs, these simulations considered a 5 mm (width) silver (Ag) frame as the ground for the FTO-mesh samples (Fig. 6b–d). As preliminarily seen for DSSCs, a perimeter design greatly enhances the charge transport, and by selecting a highly conductive material such as Ag, the frame would promote more current extraction in any edge of the substrates [92]. For the simulation, all current collector mesh designs considered: i) an initial FTO-coated glass substrate with a sheet resistance of ca. 7 $\Omega\ sq^{-1}$ (labeled as Ref.); and FTO current collectors with ii) ca. 5 μm of height, and iii) covering only ca. 15 % of the total photoactive area. These criteria aimed to balance the overall photoactive area (which is reduced by opaque lines) and conductivity (which typically increases with more/wider/thicker lines). Following a stepwise optimization, the width and distance between features on triangular (labeled as Triangles), hexagonal (labeled as Hexagons), and square-shaped (labeled as Squares) current collectors were optimized to meet abovementioned criteria. These shapes were chosen as they are the only regular polygons that tessellate, meaning they can tile a plane without gaps or overlaps. This property arises from the fact that their interior angles (60° , 90° , and 120° for Triangles, Squares and Hexagons, respectively) perfectly divide 360° , allowing for the vertices of multiple shapes to meet seamlessly at a single point [93]. This geometric constraint makes triangles, squares, and hexagons the fundamental building blocks for creating continuous uniform structures. The simulations were conducted using the same

Fig. 6. Countour results of potential gradient simulations of FTO mesh samples: (a) Ref., (b) Triangles, (c) Hexagons, (d) Squares.

Table 1
Photovoltaic parameters of DSSCs.

Device	V_{OC} (V)	J_{SC} ($mA\ cm^{-2}$)	η_{FF}	η_{PCE} (%)
Ref.	0.694	8.96	0.266	1.70
Per.	0.698	12.30	0.314	2.78
L2mm	0.694	13.64	0.292	2.85
L1mm	0.690	12.38	0.335	2.96
L0.5 mm	0.688	13.55	0.360	3.46

assumptions and simplifications outlined in Section 3.2 to ensure consistency in the analysis.

Fig. 6 plots the potential gradient of the various substrates under study when a current source of 1 A is applied at the center of each pattern feature. The simulation results suggest that integrating the Ag frame and FTO mesh current collectors significantly improves the electrical conductivity of the electrode. This improvement is evident from the potential gradient transitions observed, with the Reference (Fig. 6a) showing higher electrical fields, while Fig. 6b–d displays a decreasing trend in potential electric field values. The geometry and pattern of these collectors play a critical role in how efficiently current is extracted from large-area substrates. The triangular and hexagonal meshes exhibit a slightly better charge extraction performance near the perimeter, possibly due to a higher density of collector units. However, the square mesh offers superior charge collection in the central region of the substrate, likely due to an overall shorter electron pathway length (see Fig. S14).

The influence of increased substrate conductivity in PEC-WS performance was investigated by depositing ultrathin films of bare $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ on the developed substrates and measuring the J - V response. A photocurrent onset was observed for all samples between 1.06 and 1.12 V_{RHE} (Fig. 7). This onset potential range aligns with previous reports, which are determined by kinetic and thermodynamic factors at the semiconductor-liquid junction (SCLJ) [94]. The proposed FTO current collectors, deposited on the FTO-coated glass substrates before $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ deposition, are not expected to influence these factors at the SCLJ. Nevertheless, their effect on the substrate's conductivity influences other photoanode performance metrics. As seen in Fig. 7, the samples that included FTO-mesh current collectors outperformed the Ref. sample regarding photocurrent density. Notably, the photoanode with a Square-shaped mesh exhibited a J_{photo} of ca. 0.46 mA cm^{-2} at 1.45 V_{RHE} , which is 15 % higher than the value observed for the collector-less sample. Similar to DSSCs, the FF also increases with the addition of the current collectors, especially for the Triangles sample – Table 2. The charge extraction capabilities of this unique mesh design, particularly near the perimeter of the sample (Fig. 6b), result in a sharp photocurrent increase right after its onset under light conditions (Fig. 7a, in blue). However, from 1.40 V_{RHE} onwards, the Squares sample outperforms all others, reaching an estimated η_{device} of ca. 0.58 % at 1.45 V_{RHE} . This efficiency is ca. 23 % higher than the one obtained with the Ref. sample and 4–13 % greater than other mesh designs. The superior performance of Squares at higher applied potentials seems to correlate well with its lowest simulated potential gradient in the central region of the substrate – Fig. 6d. The potential of using this highly conductive current collector mesh

Table 2

PEC water splitting performance derived from the $J_{\text{photo}}-V$ curves of the bare $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanodes under study.

Device	Photocurrent onset (V_{RHE})	$J_{\text{photo}@1.45 \text{ VRHE}}$ (mA cm^{-2})	η_{FF}	$\eta_{\text{device}@1.45 \text{ VRHE}}$ (%)
Ref.	1.06	0.38	0.43	0.47
Triangles	1.12	0.45	0.62	0.55
Hexagons	1.04	0.42	0.53	0.51
Squares	1.10	0.47	0.49	0.58

would be even more evident in a photoelectrode prepared with more efficient light-absorbing semiconductor layers. In this scenario, the detrimental effect of the (up-scaled) substrate's resistivity is even more evident due to higher operational photocurrent densities. To simulate this effect, the prepared bare $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanodes (Squares vs Ref.) were also tested under higher simulated sunlight intensities (2 and 3 sun light intensity). The resulting J - V characteristic curves (Fig. S15) clearly show a more pronounced increase in photocurrent density with light intensity for the samples using the newly developed FTO current collectors, demonstrating their effectiveness in overcoming the FTO-glass substrate conductivity challenges in large-area PEC-WS systems operating under concentrated light [95].

After studying the efficiency of the proposed FTO current collectors, a long-term chronoamperometry test was conducted to evaluate the stability of this solution for practical PEC-WS applications. The best-performing sample, featuring a square-patterned mesh design, was kept under an applied bias of 1.45 V_{RHE} while continuously illuminated with 1 sun simulated sunlight (100 mW cm^{-2}); this potential corresponds to the photocurrent-density plateau for all the hematite samples under study, while also allows a meaningful performance value. This potential value is widely used for hematite photoelectrodes, as reported in the literature [37,74,90]. Fig. 8a plots the J_{photo} history recorded over the 100 h test, demonstrating a remarkably stable average value of ca. 0.47 mA cm^{-2} . The integrity of the photoanode, especially of the FTO current collector, is corroborated by before-and-after J - V characteristics and EIS measurements (Fig. 8b – c). The latter is crucial for the current collector's function, as any detachment of an FTO line would likely increase the system's ohmic series resistance (R_{series}), estimated from the high-frequency intercept of the Nyquist plot with the real impedance axis (Z'). As shown in Fig. 8c, R_{series} remained stable before and after the stability test, at a value 4.5 times lower than that observed for the Ref. (ca. $11.84 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ vs. ca. $53.32 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$). The remarkable stability demonstrated here is no surprise, given FTO's proven durability in aqueous solutions with a pH ranging from 0 to 14 [47]. Nevertheless,

Fig. 7. (a) J_{photo} as a function of applied potential for the bare $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanodes prepared from the substrates under study; (b) Butler plots used in the estimation of the photocurrent onset potential: horizontal intercept of the extrapolation of the linear portion of the Butler plot.

Fig. 8. (a) Current-density history obtained during the long-term chronoamperometry (CA) using the Squares sample; (b) J - V curves before and after the CA; (c) Nyquist plot obtained at the V_{OCP} before and after the CA (comparison with the data obtained for the Ref. sample).

this achievement sets a new benchmark in the field, surpassing the stability of any reported current collector by over 10-fold [68,69,96]. This validation underscores the use of highly conductive FTO lines as efficient and cost-effective current collectors for PEC-WS applications,

eliminating the need for expensive and corrosion-prone metallic materials.

4. Conclusions

This work explores the application of FTO-coated glass embedded with FTO current collectors to enhance the solar conversion efficiency of PEC devices, particularly DSSCs and PEC-WS systems. For the first time, a cost-effective method for manufacturing tunable FTO current collectors using ultrasonic spray pyrolysis has been reported, and it can be integrated with multiphysics simulations to explore various mesh designs.

Their integration into liquid-junction TiO₂-based DSSCs led to significant performance improvements, as demonstrated by conductivity simulations and experimental validation in 25 cm² DSSCs employing an FTO-line collector configuration under 1 sun illumination. Enhanced photovoltaic parameters were primarily attributed to improved electrical conductivity and reduced recombination losses. Specifically, compared with reference cells, the FTO collectors increased the FF from 0.26 to 0.36 and the J_{SC} from 9.0 to 13.6 mA cm⁻² while maintaining device stability for over 1000 h.

Moreover, multiphysics simulations were used to guide the design of an FTO-mesh current collector for α -Fe₂O₃-based photoanodes to maximize substrate conductivity and minimize loss of the photoactive area. A PEC-WS device featuring an optimized 25 cm² photoanode with a square-shaped FTO collector achieved a photocurrent density 15 % higher than that of a collector-less reference under 1 sun, with an estimated device efficiency (η_{device}) at 1.45 V_{RHE} of ca. 0.58 % and sustained the photogenerated current for more than 100 h – over ten times longer than devices using metal-based collectors. The study also revealed that using FTO collectors effectively reduced the ohmic R_{series} in the PECs.

These findings highlight the potential of FTO current collectors as a viable solution for upscaling DSSCs and PEC-WS devices without sacrificing performance, paving the way for cost-effective and scalable PEC technologies for solar energy conversion and hydrogen production.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jeffrey Capitão: Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis, Validation, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation. **Telmo da Silva Lopes:** Validation, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Leonardo Rodrigues:** Validation, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Tânia Lopes:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Paula Dias:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Dzmitry Ivanou:** Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Adélio Mendes:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237788>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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